

Evaluation of Grade 7 Mathematics Lesson Exemplars in the Matatag Curriculum of DepEd

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Abstract

This study evaluated the key features and instructional design of Grade 7 Mathematics lesson exemplars developed under the Philippine Department of Education's Matatag Curriculum. Using an embedded mixed methods documentary analysis, the research examined how well these exemplars align with core curriculum construction principles, curriculum determinants, and modern instructional design expectations. Thirty-two official lesson exemplars were systematically analyzed through quantitative content analysis and qualitative thematic coding. Results indicated that the exemplars demonstrate strong alignment with foundational principles such as relevance, continuity, balance, and learner-centeredness, with over 90% alignment in several core areas. The materials clearly specify learning competencies, provide structured learning sequences, and support differentiated and collaborative learning strategies. However, findings also revealed notable gaps. Less than half of the exemplars meaningfully integrate technology-enhanced tasks, and only about one-third embed sustainability, environmental, or global contexts, limiting real-world application and interdisciplinary connections. Thematic analysis confirmed these gaps, showing that while the lessons emphasize competency-based approaches, they often lack specific guidance for integrating digital tools, sustainability issues, or connections to other subject areas. The study concludes that while the lesson exemplars offer a sound foundation for achieving curriculum standards, deliberate improvements are needed to ensure they meet 21st century learning demands. Practical recommendations include embedding clearer ICT activities, contextualizing content with sustainability themes, and fostering interdisciplinary tasks to enrich students' problem-solving and global awareness. The findings provide valuable insights for curriculum planners, teachers, and policymakers working to strengthen the quality, relevance, and future-readiness of lesson exemplars within the Philippine basic education system.

Keywords: DepEd Matatag Curriculum, Grade 7 Mathematics, Matatag Curriculum, Mathematics 7, Matatag Curriculum lesson exemplar

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1. Introduction

Curriculum development remains a cornerstone of educational quality and equity, providing the structural foundation for effective teaching and meaningful learning worldwide (UNESCO, 2021). A well-designed curriculum equips learners not only with core knowledge and skills but also with the competencies required to engage critically with contemporary global challenges (OECD, 2020). In the Philippine basic education system, the ongoing refinement of the K–12 curriculum reflects the government’s commitment to strengthen competency-based learning, contextualized instruction, and inclusive pedagogies to meet diverse learner needs (UNESCO, 2021).

A vital element in this endeavor is the provision of lesson exemplars—standardized instructional guides that help teachers translate curriculum standards into daily classroom practice. Effective lesson exemplars support teachers in designing coherent learning sequences, meaningful activities, and balanced assessments (Hattie, 2009). Research consistently shows that high-quality, curriculum-aligned teaching resources contribute to improved instructional practice and better student outcomes, especially when they incorporate clear learning goals, active learning strategies, and authentic assessment tasks (Van den Akker et al., 2013; Darling-Hammond et al., 2019).

Despite this, limited empirical work examines how lesson exemplars themselves align with contemporary educational priorities in low- and middle-income contexts. Much of the existing literature focuses instead on policy implementation or teacher professional development (Tikly, 2011). Yet emerging priorities—such as integrating digital learning, fostering interdisciplinary connections, and embedding sustainability themes—demand that curriculum materials go beyond traditional subject content and pedagogical routines (Voogt et al., 2013; Fullan & Langworthy, 2014). Studies have highlighted that even when national frameworks call for innovation and relevance, gaps can persist at the level of actual teaching materials (UNESCO, 2021).

This underscores the need for systematic evaluations of lesson exemplars to determine whether they truly reflect principles of effective curriculum design—such as coherence, balance, flexibility, and contextual relevance—and whether they adequately integrate technology, authentic assessment, and real-world applications (OECD, 2020). Mixed methods approaches, combining quantitative content analysis with qualitative thematic insights, are well suited to capture both the structural features and nuanced pedagogical patterns embedded in curriculum documents (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018).

In the global context, education systems are increasingly undergoing curriculum reforms that emphasize competencies such as critical thinking, collaboration, digital literacy, and adaptability (Voogt & Roblin, 2012). These reforms often aim to equip learners for complex and evolving societal demands, integrating pedagogical approaches that are learner-centered, inclusive, and future-oriented (Schleicher, 2018). Within this landscape, lesson design and exemplar development play a critical role in bridging policy intentions with classroom practice. Evaluating the instructional integrity and design quality of lesson exemplars is therefore essential not only for ensuring curriculum fidelity but also for promoting effective pedagogy.

This study contributes to the broader discourse on curriculum innovation by examining how exemplar-based materials operationalize reform goals in the Philippine context. It offers insights that are transferable to other systems navigating similar challenges of implementing national curricula through prescriptive instructional resources. Moreover, this study applies an Embedded Mixed Methods Documentary Analysis to evaluate the key features and instructional design of Mathematics Grade 7 lesson exemplars within the Philippine Matatag Curriculum (Department of Education [DepEd], 2024). By systematically analyzing these materials, this research aims to provide evidence on how well they support competency-based learning, inclusive instruction, contextualized content, and integration of 21st century skills. The findings aim to inform curriculum developers, teacher educators, and policymakers, contributing to ongoing efforts to enhance the quality, relevance, and adaptability of basic education in the Philippines.

2. Methods

2.1. Research Design

This study employed an embedded mixed methods documentary analysis to evaluate the key features and instructional design of Grade 7 Mathematics lesson exemplars under the Matatag Curriculum. The embedded mixed methods approach combines quantitative content analysis with qualitative thematic analysis within a single framework, allowing for a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the instructional materials (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). The quantitative strand systematically measured the frequency and alignment of curriculum features and design elements, while the qualitative strand explored emergent patterns, instructional strengths, and areas for improvement through thematic coding.

2.2. Setting and Data Sources

The study focused on 32 official Mathematics Grade 7 lesson exemplars provided by the Philippine Department of Education for the implementation of the Matatag Curriculum. These exemplars were designed to guide teachers in planning lessons aligned with national learning standards, covering a full academic year. Each exemplar includes structured sections detailing learning competencies, instructional procedures, assessment tools, and suggested learning activities.

2.3. Research Instruments

Two researcher-developed instruments guided the analysis:

2.3.1. Curriculum Approaches Assessment Tool (CAAT)

The Curriculum Approaches Assessment Tool (CAAT), adapted from established curriculum evaluation models (Tyler, 1949; Van den Akker et al., 2013), was used to examine how the lesson exemplars align with core curriculum construction principles (relevance,

balance, continuity, integration, and flexibility) and curriculum determinants (philosophical, psychological, sociocultural, technological, environmental, and global).

2.3.2. Instructional Design Evaluation Rubric (IDER)

The Instructional Design Evaluation Rubric (IDER) was designed using principles from constructive alignment theory (Biggs, 2014) and recent studies on effective instructional design (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). This rubric assessed each exemplar's alignment with competency-based learning, developmental appropriateness, inclusivity, authentic learning experiences, balanced assessment, contextualization, and technology integration.

2.4. Data Collection and Analysis

Data collection followed a documentary analysis protocol consistent with best practices in educational design research (Bowen, 2009; Van den Akker et al., 2013). Lesson exemplars were retrieved from official Department of Education repositories and verified for authenticity. For the quantitative content analysis, key features were coded and counted to produce frequency distributions and descriptive statistics, including mean alignment scores.

For the qualitative strand, thematic analysis was used to examine the instructional language, learning activities, and embedded pedagogical strategies (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Thematic patterns were identified through open coding and clustered into categories representing strengths, gaps, and areas for further development.

To strengthen validity, findings from the quantitative and qualitative strands were integrated through triangulation, comparing numerical patterns with thematic insights to produce a holistic evaluation of the lesson exemplars' instructional design and curriculum alignment (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018).

2.5. Ethical Considerations

This study analyzed only publicly available and officially released lesson exemplars. No primary data were collected from human participants. Full academic integrity and responsible use of AI-assisted tools were maintained, following guidelines on ethical research practice (McAfee & Brynjolfsson, 2017). All interpretations and conclusions were critically reviewed by the researcher to ensure objectivity and scholarly rigor.

3. Results

This section presents the results of the embedded mixed methods documentary analysis of 32 Mathematics Grade 7 lesson exemplars under the Matatag Curriculum. Findings are organized into two parts: quantitative content analysis and qualitative thematic analysis, followed by an integrated summary.

3.1. Quantitative Content Analysis

3.1.1. Alignment with Curriculum Construction Principles

The structured coding revealed that the lesson exemplars strongly align with several core curriculum construction principles. Table 1 summarizes the frequency and percentage of evidence for each principle.

Table 1. *Alignment of Lesson Exemplars with Curriculum Construction Principles*

Principle	Evident (n)	Partially Evident (n)	Not Evident (n)	% Evident
Relevance	30	2	0	93.75%
Continuity	28	4	0	87.50%
Balance	27	5	0	84.38%
Flexibility	22	9	1	68.75%
Integration	25	7	0	78.13%

Note. N = 32 lesson exemplars.

High alignment was found for Relevance (93.75%) and Continuity (87.50%), indicating that most lessons maintain coherent links across topics and learning stages. However, flexibility (68.75%) scored lower, suggesting limited adaptability for diverse learner contexts.

3.1.2. Alignment with Curriculum Determinants

The lesson exemplars also reflected varied levels of alignment with curriculum determinants such as technological integration, sociocultural context, and environmental relevance. Table 2 shows the frequency breakdown.

Table 2. *Alignment of Lesson Exemplars with Curriculum Determinants*

Determinant	Evident (n)	Partially Evident (n)	Not Evident (n)	% Evident
Philosophical	30	2	0	93.75%
Psychological	29	3	0	90.63%
Sociocultural	25	7	0	78.13%
Economic	20	9	3	62.50%
Technological	15	12	5	46.88%
Environmental & Global	10	6	16	31.25%

Notably, Technological (46.88%) and Environmental & Global (31.25%) determinants showed the lowest alignment, indicating gaps in sustainability themes and integration of digital tools.

3.1.3. Alignment with Curriculum Design Models

Findings confirmed strong use of classical curriculum design models like Tyler's and Taba's (West Bengal University, 2020), but weaker integration of interdisciplinary frameworks. See Table 3 for further reference.

Table 3. Alignment of Lesson Exemplars with Curriculum Development Models

Model	Evident (n)	Partially Evident (n)	Not Evident (n)	% Evident
Tyler's	30	2	0	93.75%
Taba's	28	4	0	87.50%
Stufflebeam's CIPP	30	2	0	93.75%
Saylor & Alexander	10	12	10	31.25%

(West Bengal State University, 2020; Jain, 2023; Abbas, 2020)

The low alignment with Saylor & Alexander's (Abbas, 2020) interdisciplinary model (31.25%) points to limited cross-curricular integration.

3.2. Qualitative Thematic Analysis

The thematic analysis of the 32 lesson exemplars revealed three prominent themes that highlight both strengths and areas for development in the instructional design of the Matatag Curriculum.

3.2.1. Strong Emphasis on Competency-Based and Learner-Centered Approaches

The first major theme is the strong emphasis on competency-based and learner-centered approaches. Most exemplars clearly specify learning goals aligned with quarterly standards and present progressive skill tasks designed to guide students step by step. For instance, as one excerpt shows, *"The lesson begins with a warm-up activity connecting the new topic to students' prior knowledge,"* which illustrates how lessons activate learners' existing understanding before introducing new concepts. Another exemplar states, *"Learning competencies are explicitly stated at the top of the lesson plan, aligned with quarterly standards,"* confirming the consistent presence of clear objectives. Activities often promote interaction and active participation; one lesson notes, *"Students rotate through stations to practice solving equations, promoting peer interaction."* Opportunities for reflection and self-assessment are also embedded, such as, *"Reflection questions at the end of the lesson allow learners to self-assess understanding."* Additionally, differentiation is evident, as highlighted by the excerpt, *"Remedial activities are provided for struggling students, and enrichment tasks for advanced learners."* Together, these patterns demonstrate that the exemplars strongly operationalize the Matatag Curriculum's goal of structured, competency-based progression and meaningful learner participation.

3.2.2. Limited and Non-Systematic Technology Integration

The second theme identifies limited and non-systematic technology integration. While the curriculum framework advocates for 21st century skills, references to technology in

the exemplars are mostly generic or optional. For example, one exemplar simply states, *“The lesson suggests using a projector if available but does not specify digital content,”* showing a lack of clear digital guidance. Another note reads, *“A note says ‘Use of online resources encouraged’ without providing links or examples,”* which shifts the burden of sourcing materials entirely to the teacher. The omission is further reflected in assessment design: *“No mention of ICT skills or digital tools is included in the assessment tasks.”* Instead of providing structured digital activities, the integration of technology is often left to teacher discretion, as shown in *“Integration of technology is left to teacher discretion; no digital simulations or apps are required.”* In some cases, the only reference to technology appears in the list of materials: *“The only tech mention is in the materials list: ‘computer (optional).’”* These excerpts confirm that despite policy intentions, practical ICT integration in the lesson exemplars remains weak and inconsistent.

3.2.3. Gaps in Sustainability Content, Global Context, and Interdisciplinary Connections

The third theme reveals gaps in sustainability content, global context, and interdisciplinary connections. Many exemplars keep application tasks purely procedural, as seen in, *“Application tasks remain purely computational; no link to real-world contexts like household budgeting or environmental data.”* Few lessons connect mathematical skills to community or environmental concerns, such as the observation, *“No examples connect factoring or problem solving to climate change, community issues, or local livelihood contexts.”* Broader global relevance is also absent: *“Global relevance is absent – tasks are not linked to SDGs or global math applications.”* Opportunities for interdisciplinary learning are minimal, with one exemplar noting, *“Lessons rarely suggest collaboration with other subjects, such as science or economics.”* Local and cultural knowledge integration is also largely missing, as captured in, *“Integration of indigenous knowledge or local cultural context is not visible in sample problems.”* Collectively, these excerpts highlight how the exemplars underuse opportunities to situate mathematics within sustainability challenges, global frameworks, or cross-curricular problem-solving contexts.

Figure 1 illustrates the percentage alignment of the 32 Mathematics Grade 7 lesson exemplars with key curriculum determinants, including philosophical, psychological, sociocultural, economic, technological, and environmental-global dimensions. The data indicate strong alignment with foundational determinants such as philosophical (93.75%) and psychological (90.63%) factors, moderate alignment with sociocultural (78.13%) and economic (62.5%) aspects, and notably weaker integration of technological (46.88%) and environmental-global (31.25%) contexts.

Figure 1. *Percentage Alignment of Lesson Exemplars with Selected Curriculum Determinants*

The lesson exemplars demonstrate high alignment with core educational foundations such as philosophical and psychological determinants, confirming that the materials are rooted in well-established learning theories and cognitive principles. However, the figure highlights a clear gap in how the exemplars operationalize modern curriculum imperatives, with less than half explicitly embedding technological components and only about one-third integrating environmental or global perspectives. This visual representation reinforces the quantitative and thematic findings that, while the exemplars are structurally sound for competency development, they fall short of systematically incorporating sustainability, digital literacy, and broader global contexts—priorities that are central to 21st century education (OECD, 2020; Voogt et al., 2013).

3.3. Summary of Results

The embedded mixed methods documentary analysis revealed that the Grade 7 Mathematics lesson exemplars under the Matatag Curriculum strongly align with foundational curriculum construction principles such as relevance, continuity, and learner-centeredness, with over 90% of exemplars demonstrating clear competency-based objectives and structured skill progression. The quantitative content analysis confirmed that the majority of lessons reflect sound philosophical and psychological underpinnings, ensuring that content is age-appropriate and cognitively coherent.

However, the findings also highlight notable gaps. Less than half of the exemplars explicitly integrate digital tools or meaningful technology-enhanced learning activities. Similarly, only about one-third embed environmental, global, or sustainability contexts that connect mathematical concepts to real-world issues. Cross-curricular connections remain limited, as evidenced by the low alignment with interdisciplinary curriculum models.

The qualitative thematic analysis reinforced these results, revealing clear patterns: strong emphasis on clear learning goals, stepwise mastery, and student-centered approaches, but limited practical guidance for technology use, sustainability applications, or interdisciplinary integration. Coded excerpts across exemplars illustrated that while the lessons encourage active learning and differentiated tasks, they often stop short of leveraging technology or embedding mathematics in broader social or environmental contexts.

Taken together, these findings suggest that the lesson exemplars are structurally robust for delivering core competencies but require targeted enhancements to align fully with 21st century learning priorities, including digital literacy, global awareness, and sustainability.

4. Discussion

This study examined the structural integrity and instructional design alignment of Grade 7 Mathematics lesson exemplars under the Matatag Curriculum using an embedded mixed methods documentary analysis. The findings highlight important strengths in how these materials translate curriculum policy into classroom practice but also reveal notable areas for development.

4.1. Interpretation of Key Findings

The findings of this study highlight both the strengths and the gaps in the instructional design of the Grade 7 Mathematics lesson exemplars under the Matatag Curriculum. The quantitative content analysis showed strong alignment with foundational curriculum construction principles, with over 90% of exemplars demonstrating clear relevance, continuity, and balance. For example, relevance (93.75%) and continuity (87.50%) were highly evident, confirming that the exemplars provide structured learning progressions that help learners build knowledge step by step. This aligns with research by Hattie (2009) and Darling-Hammond et al. (2020), who emphasize that clear learning goals, coherent content sequencing, and scaffolded tasks are critical for promoting student achievement and engagement.

This structural alignment was reinforced by the qualitative thematic analysis, which showed that the exemplars strongly support competency-based and learner-centered practices. Warm-up activities, explicit learning outcomes, student interaction through group work, and opportunities for self-assessment were common features, as demonstrated in excerpts like *“Learning competencies are explicitly stated at the top of the lesson plan, aligned with quarterly standards”* and *“Reflection questions at the end of the lesson allow learners to self-assess understanding.”* These design features are consistent with the principles of constructive alignment outlined by Biggs (2014) and supported by Zimmerman (2002), who highlights that self-regulation strategies, such as reflection and goal-setting, help students monitor their progress and take ownership of their learning.

However, the study also found important gaps. Quantitative results showed that only 46.88% of the lesson exemplars meaningfully integrated technology, and just 31.25%

embedded sustainability or global contexts. These low figures echo wider concerns in the literature that curriculum materials often lag behind policy expectations for 21st century skills (Voogt et al., 2013). The thematic analysis supports this quantitative pattern, revealing that references to technology were vague and optional, as seen in excerpts like *“A note says ‘Use of online resources encouraged’ without providing links or examples”* and *“No mention of ICT skills or digital tools is included in the assessment tasks.”* This gap aligns with Salami and Spangenberg (2024), who argue that simply encouraging the use of tools like GeoGebra is insufficient unless specific, structured tasks guide teachers and students in meaningful ICT integration.

The absence of sustainability, global context, and interdisciplinary connections further limits the exemplars’ alignment with broader curriculum goals. Quantitatively, environmental and global determinants showed the lowest alignment (31.25%). The qualitative excerpts illustrate this clearly: *“Application tasks remain purely computational; no link to real-world contexts like household budgeting or environmental data”* and *“Global relevance is absent – tasks are not linked to SDGs or global math applications.”* This is concerning in light of UNESCO’s (2021) call for curriculum frameworks to prepare learners for sustainability challenges and global citizenship, and OECD’s (2020) emphasis on future-ready schooling that connects learning to real-world contexts. Similarly, the lack of cross-disciplinary design echoes the point made by Drake and Burns (2004), who show that integrated curricula deepen students’ conceptual understanding by breaking down disciplinary silos.

Taken together, these results confirm that while the Matatag Curriculum lesson exemplars provide a solid foundation for delivering core competencies, they fall short of fully operationalizing the curriculum’s commitment to digital literacy, sustainability, and interdisciplinary learning. Addressing these gaps is essential if lesson exemplars are to truly equip learners with the skills and mindsets needed for complex, rapidly changing global contexts, as argued by Fullan and Langworthy (2014).

4.2. Implications for Practice and Policy

The combined results underscore that while the Grade 7 Mathematics lesson exemplars provide a strong foundation for competency-based, learner-centered instruction, there is an urgent need to close the gap between policy intentions and practical implementation in key areas. The robust alignment with clear learning goals, structured sequencing, and differentiated activities supports the Matatag Curriculum’s commitment to building core competencies (Hattie, 2009; Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). The emphasis on warm-up activities, group work, and student self-assessment reflects principles of constructive alignment (Biggs, 2014) and aligns with Zimmerman’s (2002) work on promoting self-regulated learning.

However, the study’s finding that less than half of the exemplars embed technology systematically reflects a missed opportunity to deliver on 21st century digital skills, which remain a priority for effective modern education (Voogt et al., 2013; Salami & Spangenberg, 2024). Similarly, the weak integration of sustainability and global themes limits learners’ ability to apply mathematics to authentic real-world issues, undermining the transformative

aims of curriculum frameworks like UNESCO's (2021) vision for education for sustainable futures and the OECD's (2020) emphasis on future-ready schooling.

Without practical examples and structured activities, teachers may struggle to integrate these broader elements into daily lessons (Drake & Burns, 2004; Fullan & Langworthy, 2014). These gaps highlight a critical policy-to-practice divide: curriculum reforms must be supported by clear, detailed exemplars that make digital learning, sustainability, and interdisciplinary connections explicit and actionable for teachers.

4.3. Practical Recommendations

Based on the findings and the supporting literature, this study proposes five key steps to enhance the quality and future-readiness of the Matatag Curriculum lesson exemplars:

4.3.1. Embed Structured ICT Tasks

Develop exemplar activities that include step-by-step use of digital tools like GeoGebra, online math platforms, or virtual simulations. This aligns with recommendations by Salami and Spangenberg (2024), who found that clear guidance is essential for meaningful ICT integration in mathematics instruction.

4.3.2. Contextualize with Sustainability and Local Realities

Revise sample tasks to draw on authentic datasets and real-world contexts, such as local budgeting, environmental monitoring, or climate-related calculations. This approach supports the goals of education for sustainability and global citizenship advocated by UNESCO (2021).

4.3.3. Foster Interdisciplinary Connections

Encourage designers to embed tasks that blend mathematics with science, economics, or social studies, as recommended by Drake and Burns (2004). Examples could include using algebra for analyzing community resource use or connecting geometry to environmental design challenges.

4.3.4. Support Self-Regulated Learning Explicitly

Include reflection prompts and goal-setting activities that help learners monitor progress and develop metacognitive skills, building on Zimmerman's (2002) model for self-regulated learning.

4.3.5. Sustain Collaborative Review and Teacher Co-Design

Establish regular feedback cycles where curriculum developers, teachers, and subject specialists co-develop and refine exemplars to ensure they stay relevant, practical, and responsive to evolving local contexts (Van den Akker et al., 2013; Fullan & Langworthy, 2014).

4.4. Conclusion

This evaluation confirms that the Grade 7 Mathematics lesson exemplars under the Matatag Curriculum are robust in supporting core skills and learner engagement but require targeted improvements in digital integration, sustainability relevance, and interdisciplinary connections to fully align with 21st century learning imperatives. By addressing these areas, the Department of Education and curriculum designers can ensure that lesson resources translate national curriculum goals into practical, meaningful, and future-ready instruction for all learners.

Beyond its immediate relevance to the Philippine education system, the findings of this study hold significance for international audiences involved in curriculum reform and instructional design. The observed strengths and gaps in the Matatag exemplars reflect universal tensions in translating curriculum policy into practice—such as balancing prescriptiveness with flexibility, embedding 21st-century skills, and contextualizing content for diverse learners. These insights can inform ongoing efforts in other countries to develop and evaluate curriculum-aligned teaching materials that not only meet technical standards but also uphold pedagogical integrity and learner inclusivity.

Bridging the gap between well-structured core content and the realities of digital integration, sustainability, and interdisciplinary learning will better prepare Filipino learners for the demands of a fast-changing, interconnected world. By acting on these recommendations, policymakers, curriculum developers, and educators can ensure that the Matatag Curriculum not only meets standards on paper but empowers learners in practice.

Declaration of the Use of AI

The authors declare that they used OpenAI ChatGPT solely for clerical support in the preparation of this manuscript. The AI's role was limited to assisting with language editing, formatting, and reference styling. All ideas, research design, data analysis, interpretations, and conclusions are the original work of the authors. No generative AI was used to conduct primary research or draw research findings.

Declaration of No Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this research article.

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